

Stabilities of the Metal Complexes of Some Nuclear-Substituted Derivatives of Diphenylcarbazone

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Stability constants of Cu(II), Zn(II), Ni(II) and Mg(II) complexes of several nuclear-substituted derivatives of diphenylcarbazone have been determined by the Calvin-Bjerrum technique in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxane. The acid dissociation constants of the ligands used are reported and the influence of substitution in the phenyl rings of diphenylcarbazone is discussed.

ALTHOUGH diphenylcarbazone (dpc) was introduced as an analytical reagent much earlier than its sulphur analogue, dithizone, it has received considerably less importance as a ligand in the study of metal complexes. Some of the nuclear-substituted derivatives of dpc are in fact found to be very sensitive to metals and give intense colouration with them. Although they are capable of being developed as useful analytical reagents, not much attention has been paid to them. The work reported here has been undertaken to study the solution equilibria involving several of these nuclear-substituted derivatives of dpc with some bivalent metal ions in 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxane, as these reagents as well as their metal complexes are sparingly soluble in water.

Experimental

All the metal salt solutions were prepared by dissolving calculated amounts of their sulphates (AnalaR grade) in double distilled water and diluting them to the required volume to get approximately 0.05 M solutions. EDTA titrations were employed to determine the metal ion concentration in each.

Dioxane (B. D. H., AnalaR) was further purified by the method of Freiser *et al.*¹. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by the method of Allen and Low².

For the preparation of di(*o*-tolyl)carbazone, a calculated quantity of *o*-tolylhydrazine (8 g) was mixed thoroughly with guaicolcarbonate (5 g). The temp. of the mixture was raised gradually to 160° and maintained at this for 3 hr. It was cooled and allowed to stand overnight in a refrigerator. The pasty mass thus obtained was boiled with benzene (25 ml), cooled and filtered. On evaporation of benzene, di(*o*-tolyl)carbazide was obtained. It was recrystallised from benzene and oxidised to di(*o*-tolyl)carbazone as described by Ghosh and Ray³. The di(*o*-tolyl)carbazone and the di(2,4-xylyl)carbazone were prepared by similar methods.

The di(*o*-, *p*- and *m*-nitrophenyl)carbazones were prepared according to Krumholz *et al.*⁴. The corresponding carbazides were oxidised to their carbazones as described above but at an elevated temperature.

The pH measurements were carried out with a Toshniwal Model CL-43 pH-meter, equipped with glass and calomel electrodes. It was calibrated with a 0.05 N potassium hydrogen phthalate buffer and further checked with phosphate (pH=6.85 at 25°) and borax (pH=9.18 at 25°) buffers. All the titrations against standard sodium hydroxide were carried out in an inert atmosphere in a specially designed double-walled beaker, as per the Calvin-Bjerrum technique involving (i) the titration of free perchloric acid solution ($E^{\circ}=0.01 M$), (ii) the titration of free perchloric acid, and the reagent solution ($T_{M}^{\circ}=0.0025 M$) and (iii) the titration of free perchloric acid, the reagent and the metal solution ($T_{M}^{\circ}=0.0005 M$).

The temperature, the ionic strength and the composition of the medium were maintained at 25°, 0.1 M NaClO₄ and 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxane, respectively.

Proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants :

The \bar{n}_A values of dpc and its derivatives were calculated by regarding them as monobasic acids, by using the expression :

$$\bar{n}_A = 1 - \frac{(v'' - v')(N + E^{\circ})}{(V^{\circ} + v')T_2^{\circ}}$$

where v'' and v' are the volumes of alkali of normality N added in titrations (i) and (ii), respectively to reach the same value of pH.

The pK_A values of these reagents were obtained from the plots of \bar{n}_A vs pH at $\bar{n}_A=0.5$, as well as from the intercepts of the linear plots of $\log [\bar{n}_A/(1 - \bar{n}_A)]$ vs pH.

For the purpose of calculating the metal-ligand stability constants, \bar{n} values were obtained from the

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Irving and Rossotti expression⁶. $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were then obtained from the plots of \bar{n} vs pL , from the half-integral values. In the case of Ni(II), which forms 1 : 3 complexes in addition to 1 : 1 and 1 : 2, the $\log K_3$ values were obtained both by the half-integral method and the linear plots of $-\log(3 - \bar{n}) / (\bar{n} - 2)$ vs pL .

Results and Discussion

Table 1 summarises the acid dissociation constants of dpc and its nuclear-substituted derivatives investigated in this work. For comparison, the corresponding values for dithizone and four of the substituted dithizones, available in literature have been included. It may be seen that the latter are considerably lower than the corresponding dpc values. This is consistent with the greater electro-negativity of oxygen as compared to that of sulphur.

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF DIPHENYLCARBAZONE AND ITS NUCLEAR SUBSTITUTED DERIVATIVES

Reagent	Diphenylcarbazone (This work)	Dithizone (Ref. 14)
1. Unsubstituted	9.26*	5.80
2. <i>p</i> -Nitroderivative	6.56	—
3. <i>o</i> -Nitroderivative	6.46	—
4. <i>m</i> -Nitroderivative	7.69	—
5. <i>o</i> -Methyl derivative	9.58	6.28
6. <i>p</i> -Methyl derivative	9.75	6.40
7. 2,4-Xylyl derivative	10.00	6.87

* Also from Ref. 14.

Table 2 summarises the metal-ligand stability constants of the diphenylcarbazones. The values given for the complexes of di(*m*-nitrophenyl)carbazone are to be regarded as unreliable, on account of the formation of precipitate on addition of alkali, and may be ignored for the purpose of discussion. Although precipitation also occurs in the case of Cu(II) and Zn(II) with the methylsubstituted ligands, the measurements made only up to the point of precipitation have been included in the calculations of stability constants.

The $\log K_1$ values of complexes are in the order Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II) > Mg(II). This is in agreement with the order given by Mellor and Maley⁶

and Irving and Williams⁷. The comparatively large value of $\log K_1$ for Cu(II) may be attributed to the possible formation of a square planar complex, in which the $4p_x$ orbitals of copper, which are perpendicular to the chelate ring may be delocalised and hence may contribute to greater stability. Similar conclusions were also drawn by Charles and Freiser⁸ in explaining the $\log K_1$ values of Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes of dimethylglyoxime, which differ by less than one unit. In this case, Ni(II) also forms a square planar complex.

The small differences in $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ values may be attributed to the fact that the first chelation takes place with partial neutralisation of charge on the central metal ion, while the second completely neutralises it. The resulting complex will have minimum polarity, thereby relieving the entire complex molecule from the solvation effect and consequent increase in the entropy of the complex.

The observed $\log K$ values also show the effect of substitution on the stability constants of the complexes. The introduction of the electron-withdrawing nitrogroup tends to make the ligand a poorer donor; this is reflected in the smaller stability constants of these complexes compared to those of unsubstituted dpc. The methyl substitution, on the other hand, enhances the donor strength on account of their electron repelling tendency, accounting for the higher stabilities observed for the di(*p*-tolyl)carbazone complexes. One would expect that the di(2,4-xylyl)carbazone complexes, on this basis, be still stronger, but results show that this is not the case. The explanation may lie in the possibility of steric hindrance as discussed below.

Earlier studies of dpc complexes have shown⁹⁻¹² that the complex formation takes place between $-O^-$ and $-N<$ of the ligand and the metal ions. The formation of the 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes may be represented as in the diagram shown below.

It can be seen from the diagram that the substitution in the *ortho* position to the N-H group can cause steric hindrance; this is the case in the di(*o*-tolyl)carbazone as well as di(2,4-xylyl)carbazone.

The proton-ligand and metal-ligand equilibria being similar, viz., $M + L \rightleftharpoons ML$ and $H + L \rightleftharpoons HL$, it is

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF SOME METAL COMPLEXES WITH SOME NUCLEAR SUBSTITUTED DIPHENYLCARBAZONES AT 25°

Ligand	Cu(II)		Ni(II)			Zn(II)		Mg(II)	
	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_3$	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log \beta_1$	$\log \beta_2$
1. Diphenylcarbazone	9.16	18.08	6.71	12.84	17.51	6.39	12.43	3.08	—
2. Di(<i>o</i> -nitrophenyl)carbazone	6.69	12.92	4.70	8.82	—	4.13	7.73	—	—
3. Di(<i>p</i> -nitrophenyl)carbazone	6.81	13.41	5.32	10.28	—	4.75	8.96	2.83	—
4. Di(<i>m</i> -nitrophenyl)carbazone	8.34	16.50	7.40	14.40	—	6.88	13.43	—	—
5. Di(<i>o</i> -tolyl)carbazone	8.16	15.82	5.67	10.81	15.01	5.19	9.97	2.96	—
6. Di(<i>p</i> -tolyl)carbazone	10.19	10.03	7.22	13.86	—	7.00	18.83	3.34	6.40
7. Di(2,4-xylyl)carbazone	9.81	19.28	5.82	11.00	15.30	5.76	11.24	3.02	—

reasonable to expect a simple relationship to exist between the acid dissociation constant of the proton-ligand complex and the stability constant of the metal-ligand complex. Fig. 1 depicts this relationship between the $\log K_1$ values of the metal complexes and the pK_a values of the ligands, which is found to be linear in the case of Cu(II), Ni(II) and

another metal. Fig. 2 shows the $\log K_1$ values of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Mg(II) complexes plotted against those of Zn(II). Such a linear relationship is indeed found in the case of Ni(II) and Mg(II), although

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log K_1$ values of the metal-ligand complexes vs pK_a values of the various substituted carbazones.

1. diphenylcarbazone, 2. di(*p*-nitrophenyl)carbazone, 3. di(*o*-nitrophenyl)carbazone, 4. di(*m*-nitrophenyl)carbazone, 5. di(*o*-tolyl)carbazone, 6. di(*p*-tolyl)carbazone and 7. di(2,4-xylyl)carbazone.

Zn(II). The fact that the points corresponding to *o*-tolyl and 2,4-xylyl substituents show a marked departure from linearity in each case is possibly the result of steric hindrance, as already pointed out. This effect is also observed to some extent in the case of the di(*o*-nitrophenyl)carbazone complexes of Zn(II) and Ni(II), although it is comparatively minor.

Freiser and co-workers¹⁸ suggested that correlations can also be made with the complexes of

Fig. 2. Plot of $\log K_1$ of Zn(II)-ligand complexes vs the $\log K_1$ values of the Cu(II), Ni(II) and Mg(II) complexes of the corresponding ligands.

1. diphenylcarbazone, 2. di(*p*-nitrophenyl)carbazone, 3. di(*o*-nitrophenyl)carbazone, 4. di(*m*-nitrophenyl)carbazone, 5. di(*o*-tolyl)carbazone, 6. di(*p*-tolyl)carbazone and 7. di(2,4-xylyl)carbazone.

Cu(II) shows pronounced departure from linearity. This may be attributed to the existence of identical structures for the complexes of Zn(II), Ni(II) and Mg(II). Ni(II) has been shown to give octahedral complexes with diphenylcarbazone and its derivatives, as it forms 1:3 complexes in some cases. Cu(II) on the other hand forms square planar complexes.

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